

~~Maheन्द्र~~ Sanskrit University

One Year B.Ed.

Compulsory Course

Educational Psychology

Course No:Ed 3002

Course duration : 150 hrs.

Nature of course : Theoretical

Number of period : 180

Full Marks : 100

Period per weeks : 6

Pass Marks : 35

Time per period : 50 min.

Course Description: This is a course on educational psychology. The course has nine units. Unit one deals with the meaning and scope of educational psychology. Unit two and three deal with the developmental aspects of learners, specially the students of secondary schools level. Unit four, five and six deal with learning, theories of learning, factors affecting learning and basic instructional procedure. Unit seven and eight deal with evaluation of learning outcome; it's concept, tools and techniques and Unit nine deals with guidance and counseling of students.

General Objective: The general objective of this course is to acquaint the teacher trainees with the concept of educational psychology and its scope, learner, learning process and conditions, process of instruction and the process of guidance and counseling.

Specific Objectives: On the completion of this course the trainees will be able to:

- discuss the meaning and scope of educational psychology,
- explain the concept of human growth and development, it's processes and determinants,
- describe the various stages of human development,
- describe the developmental characteristics of secondary school level students,
- enumerate different theories of learning with their implications to instruction.
- identify the factors affecting learning process.
- discuss the basic tents of instructional process.
- explain the concept of evaluation and measurement,
- identify and use the tools and techniques for evaluation and
- explain the concept and process of educational guidance and counseling

Course Content

Unit I.	Introduction to Educational Psychology	8 periods
Unit II.	Human Growth and Development	17 periods
Unit III.	Developmental Characteristic of Secondary Level Students	20 periods
Unit IV	Introduction to Learning and its Theories	40 periods
Unit V	Factors Affecting Learning	20 periods
Unit VI	Basic Instructional Procedure	20 periods
Unit VII	Evaluation and Measurement	7 periods
Unit VIII	Evaluation Tools and Techniques	33 periods
Unit IX	Guidance and Counseling	15 periods
		Total 180 periods

Course content in detail

Unit I: Introduction to Educational Psychology

- 1.1. Meaning and definition of educational psychology
- 1.2. Scope of educational psychology
 - Identification of learner (Human development)
 - Teaching process
 - Measurement of learning outcomes
 - Guidance and counseling
- 1.3. Relevance and significance of educational psychology for teachers and parents

Unit II : Human Growth and Development

- 2.1. Meaning of developmental changes Growth and development
- 2.2. Processes of human growth and development-Maturation and learning
- 2.3. Determinates of human growth and development-Heredity and environment
- 2.4. Stages of human growth and development (From conception to old age with general characteristics)
- 2.5. Methods of studying human growth and development
 - Longitudinal
 - Cross sectional
- 2.6. Importance of studying human development

Unit III: Developmental Characteristics of a Secondary School Level Student

- Developmental tasks
- Puberty growth spurt
- Effects of changes during puberty

- Hazards of puberty
- Unhappiness of Puberty
- 3.2. Developmental characteristics of an adolescent:
 - Stages in adolescent period
 - Developmental Tasks
 - Emotionality
 - Social changes
 - Changes in morality
 - Personality development
 - Hazards and Happiness
- 3.3. Teacher's role as a guide and counselor for the development of the person at puberty and adolescent stage.

Unit IV: Introduction to Learning and It's Theories

- 4.1. Learned vs. unlearned behavior
 - Concept of learning
 - Modification of behavior
 - Definition of learning
 - Unlearned behavior
 - Reflexes
 - Instincts
 - Maturation
- 4.2. Learning theories and it's issues
- 4.3. Theories of learning
 - (a) Classical conditioning: Experiment, process of learning, specific features-reinforcement, extinction and inhibition, generalization and discrimination, higher order conditioning; Classroom implications-formation and breaking of habits, teaching and learning of discipline.
 - (b) Operant conditioning: Experiment, process of learning, specific features-respondent and operant behavior, reinforcement, contingency management, behavior shaping and their class room implications, programmed instruction
 - (c) Trial and error learning: Experiment, process of learning, laws of learning, specific features-multiple response learning and chaining, belongingness and associative shifting, class room implications of trial and error learning-readiness and learning, role of reward and punishment. Role of practice.
 - (d) Insightful learning theory: Kohler's experiment, process of learning, specific features – role of perception in learning. Role of central mediation mechanism. Discovering new relationship. Sudden change in behavior, educational implication of insightful learning theory

(e) Gagne's hierarchy of learning and its educational implications.

Unit V: Factors Affecting Learning Process

- 5.1. Entering behavior: Concept, types and instructional use
- 5.2. Motivation: Concept, types, Maslow's hierarchy of motivation and use
- 5.3. Reinforcement: Concept, types—positive, negative and vicarious and use
- 5.4. Practice: concept, types and use
- 5.5. Memory and forgetting: Concept, types of memory, process of memorization, techniques for improving memory, Concept and types of forgetting, factors responsible for forgetting
- 5.6. Transfer of learning: Concept, types and use

Unit VI: Basic Instructional Procedure

- 6.1. Verbal Learning: Concept, condition, instruction in verbal knowledge.
- 6.2. Concept learning: Meaning and types of concept, instruction of concept.
- 6.3. Principle learning: Meaning of principle, induction of principle
- 6.4. Problem solving: Nature and instruction of problem solving.
- 6.5. Creativity: Meaning and instruction for creativity.
- 6.6. Discovery learning: Meaning and instruction for discovery learning.

Unit VII: Evaluation and Measurement

- 7.1. Concept of evaluation and measurement
- 7.2. Types of evaluation : Formative, summative and diagnostic
- 7.3. Importance of evaluation

Unit VIII: Evaluation Tools & Techniques

- 8.1. Testing devices
 - 8.1.1. Evaluations tools for written examination-subjective and objective items (types, strength and weakness construction of tools)
 - 8.1.2. Oral test
 - 8.1.3. Teacher made test and standardized test-concept and construction
 - 8.1.4. Item analysis
 - 8.1.5. Qualities of evaluation tools - Reliability and validity (Concept and types)
- 8.2. Non-Testing devices
 - 8.2.1. Observation : Concept, types and tools of observation rating scale, check list
- 8.3. Analysis of test results Mean, median, percentile rank, standard deviation and their use in evaluation
- 8.4. Use of test results

Unit IX: Guidance and Counseling

- 9.1 Educational guidance - Definition and emaning
 9.2 Need of guidance
 9.3 Form of guidance - Group and individual
 9.4 Techniques in guidance - Interview, case study, anecdotal record, cumulative record
 9.5 Counseling: Definitions and meaning
 9.6 Approaches to counseling - directive and electric approach
 9.7 Importance of counseling

Instructional Techniques:

- Discussion and demonstration
- Lecture/exposition and explanation
- Simulation and role-play
- Individual and group work
- Self study

Assessment Techniques and Mark Distribution

Written examination 100 Marks

Unit wise mark distribution

Unit 1, 2, 3	25 marks
Unit 4	25 marks
Unit 5, 6, 7	25 marks
Unit 8, 9	25 marks

Question wise mark distribution

20 Multiple questions	$20 \times 1 = 20$ marks
2 Long answer questions	$2 \times 12 = 24$ marks
8 Short answer question	$8 \times 7 = 56$ marks

References

1. Hurlock, E.B. (1980) *Developmental Psychology, a life span approach*. New Delhi: Tata Mc Graw Hill Publishing Company.
2. Bower, G.H. and E.R, Hilgard (1986) *Theories of Learning*, New Delhi: Prentice-Hall of India Pvt. Ltd.,
3. Dececco, John. P, (1970) *The Psychology of Learning and Instruction*, New Delhi: Prentice - Hall of India Pvt. Ltd.
4. Aggrawal. J.C., (1995) *Essential of Educational Psychology*. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing Hosue Pvt. Ltd.
5. Rao, S. Narayana. (1997) *Counseling and Guidance*. New Delhi: Tata Mc Graw Hill Publishing Company.
6. Pathak, Ganga, (2055) *Shikshya Manobigyan*, Kathmandu: Taleju Prakashan.

